

Effectiveness of Working Capital Management on Business Profitability and Liquidity: An Evidence from Manufacturing SMEs in Kitwe, Zambia

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Manufacturing Sector Liquidity Profitability Small and Medium Enterprises Working Capital Management</p>	<p>The effectiveness of working capital is a critical aspect of financial management for Small and Medium Enterprise (SMESs) in the manufacturing sector, as it directly impacts their profitability and overall business performance in many developing nations including Zambia. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Zambia's manufacturing sector faces challenges in managing their working capital that results to operational inefficiencies, lower profitability, and increasing chances of business failure. This study aimed to examine the influence of working capital management (WCM) on the performance of SMEs manufacturing sector in Kitwe, Zambia. The study employed a mixed-method design with the sample size of 200 were randomly collected and analyzed using the STATA and thematic analysis. The chi-square test reveals a statistically significant association between working capital management (WCM), Profitability ($\chi^2 = 229.150$, $p = 0.00$) and between WCM and liquidity ($\chi^2 = 565.490$, $p = 0.00$), indicating that working capital management has a significant impact either positive or negative on both profitability and liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The Pearson correlation coefficient confirmed a strong positive relationship between working capital management (WCM), and profitability ($r = 0.795$, $p = 0.000$), as well as between WCM and liquidity ($r = 0.957$, $p = 0.000$), suggesting that effective WCM is associated with increased profitability and enhanced ability of SMEs to meet their short-term obligations, thereby improving liquidity. The study concluded that SMEs should implement the formal working capital policies, enhance financial knowledge, and adopt digital financial systems to boost efficiency. Furthermore, government should also improve access to reasonably priced credit and provide business infrastructure that supports it in order to foster an enabling environment.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) played an increasingly important role in driving economic growth, innovation as well as creation of employment in late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. This viewpoint shifted from focusing on large corporations to acknowledging the dynamic and agile nature of smaller businesses (Lamichhane 2019). A parallel development in business finance was the ongoing challenge of financial distress and failure among the SMEs, which was frequently linked to inefficient financial management practices (Brammah et al. 2021). In spite of having a lot of studies on corporate finance, the specific operational and financial dynamics of SMEs, especially in developing economies like Zambia, remained a hot topic among academics (Sensini and Vazquez 2021).

In the past, working capital management (WCM) was mostly seen as a trade-off between profitability and liquidity (Anton and Afloarei-Nucu 2020). Lamprey (2021) argued that higher levels of working capital, or current assets, were thought to be prudent for preserving liquidity, by doing so came at the expense of decreased profitability because the capital was invested in non-earning assets. On the other hand, Fernández-López et al. (2020) aggressive WCM, which is defined by low current assets, may increase profitability but also increases the risk of insolvency. Prša (2020) noted that enterprises that invest more in working capital can expect lower levels of business risk, but unfavourable influences on profitability levels.

Strong financial ecosystem and advantageous credit terms were common way that policy environment in developed countries helped SMEs. However, things were very different in developing nations like Zambia. Zambian SMEs frequently faced difficult operating conditions in the late 20th century and early 2000s, marked by high interest rate, limited access reasonably priced external financing, and a preponderance or informal business practices (Kayombo 2023). A unique viewpoint emerged as a result of the setting effective internal financial management, especially WCM, was seen as vital survival tactic rather than just a way to maximize profits (Zimba and Kabubi 2025).

Zambia’s economy has traditionally been dominated by the copper mining sector, Kitwe emerging as a key hub. Ketani (2024) noted that local economy and its SMEs were regularly impacted by boom-bust cycles of global commodity prices as a result of this historical development. The regions manufacturing SMEs were under tremendous pressure to maintain steady cash flows and efficient resource management due to the inherent volatility (Zimba and Kabubi 2025). The effects of inadequate WCM, such as liquidity crises, an inability to fulfil supplier obligations, or failure to invest in new technologies, could be especially severe in this particular context due to the local economic conditions which could result in higher rate of business failure.

In order to better understand on how these conditions made working capital management more difficult how various management approaches impacted the survival and expansion of Kitwe’s manufacturing SME researcher went to work. In order to benefit the Kitwe business community and advance the global understanding of the SMEa finance, this study aimed to offer a particular, empirically supported insights into these local dynamics.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

SMEs in Kitwe face challenges with prolonged cash conversion cycles, poor accounts receivable turnover, and inadequate inventory management, negatively impacting profitability and liquidity potential (Deloof 2003). These issues are particularly problematic for SME wish limited access to external financing, making them reliant on internal cashflow for daily operations (Garcia-Tecuel and Martinez-Solano 2007). The situation is worsened by limited managerial expertise and lack of robust financial management frameworks. Although existing literature review effective working capital management to firm performance, there is a significant research gap on how these principles apply to SMEs in Zambia’s manufacturing sector, where regulatory frameworks differ from those developed economies. This study aims to examine the effectiveness of WCM on businesses performance of SMEs in Kitwe District’s manufacturing sector, exploring how WCM components influence profitability and liquidity.

1.3 Research Objectives

The general and specific objectives of this study are as presented in the sections below.

1.3.1 General Objective

Examine the Effectiveness of Working Capital Management on Business Profitability and Liquidity: An Evidence of Manufacturing SMEs in Kitwe, Zambia

1.3.2 Specific Objectives:

- i. To analyse the effect of working capital management on profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.
- ii. To establish the effect of working capital management on liquidity of SMEs in manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

1.3.3 Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of working capital management on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district?
- ii. What is the effect of working capital management on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district?

1.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study illustrates the relationship between the independent variable (Working Capital Management Practices) and the dependent variable (Business Performance). The framework also includes mediating variables such as profitability and Liquidity Management, which are critical in understanding the direct and indirect effects of WCM on business performance.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

Agency theory deals with the people who own a business enterprise and all others who have interest in it like managers, banks, creditors, family members and employees. The agency theory postulates that the day to day running of a business enterprise is carried out by managers as the agents who have been engaged by the owners of the business as principals who are also known as shareholders. This theory places emphasis on transaction costs and contracting analysis following the work of Coase (1937) Jensen and Meckling (1976) and most important, Stiglitz and Weiss (1981).

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study of working capital management practices and business performance of SMEs provides points out into the feasible and desirable growth pattern. Since SMEs dominate industrial scene in developing countries, their profitability understanding is very significant to the government, entrepreneurs, research institutions and the community (Sunday, 2011).

2. Literature Review

In his study Ketani (2024) examined working capital management and the profitability of small and medium enterprises in Nakuru Municipality using a sample of 61 enterprises and found a positive relationship between current ratio and profitability as well as debt ratio and profitability. He however found a negative relationship between cash conversion cycle and profitability. His measurement for profitability was return on assets (ROA) (Ketani, 2024). The context of the study was on small and medium enterprises in Kenya which is different from Zambia thus creating a knowledge gap.

In the study Enqvist Et al, (2014) they did an analysis of the profitability of the top six commercial banks in Tanzania and outlined the determinants of bank profitability being return on assets, return on equity or the net interest margin. The study used ROA as a measure of profitability. It revealed that bank capital strength, operations expenses, bank size, ownership and diversification influence profitability of the top six commercial banks significantly (Enqvist Et al, 2014). The study was not comprehensive on the relationship between the study variables hence cannot be used for benchmark thus creating a knowledge gap.

Lung'aho (2018) researched on WC and profitability of firms listed under the construction and Allied sector at the Nairobi securities Exchange, Kenya and her determinants of profitability were return on assets and net income. She found out that cash conversion cycle and average payment period were positively correlated with profitability but found an inverse relationship between profitability and average collection period and inventory holding period (Lung'aho, 2018). The context of the study was on s construction and Allied sector at the Nairobi securities Exchange which is different from manufacturing companies in Zambian context thus creating a knowledge gap (Enqvist Et al, 2014).

According to Gill and Mathur (2010) Liquidity management refers to the ability of a firm to meet its short-term obligations without experiencing cash flow problems. Effective WCM plays a crucial role in ensuring sufficient liquidity by balancing current assets and liabilities (Lung'aho, 2018). Researchers such as Afza and Nazir (2017) have established that firms with better liquidity management practices tend to have a competitive edge as they can seize market opportunities swiftly without resorting to costly external financing.

Enqvist et al. (2014) observed that it is so challenging to maintaining liquidity for SMEs in the manufacturing sector because of the need for bigger upfront investment in raw materials and production. Macharia (2018) noted that maintaining optimal levels of cash, receivables, and inventory is critical for liquidity on Zambia's SMEs in manufacturing industry. Afza and Nazir (2017) pointed out that poorly managed liquidity often led to insolvency or the need to secure expensive short-term loan.

Gill and Mathur (2010) found that effective management of working capital components such as inventory, account receivable, and account payable directly influence a firm's liquidity and wealth. Singh and Saini (2020) discovered that actually firms with optimistic working capital management practices experience improved liquidity. Empirically, Gupta and Singh (2018) found a positive correlation between efficiency working capital management and improved wealth ratios. Sunday (2011) emphasized that a well-manage working capital has stronger financial positions and lower debt levels.

Musonda (2020) examined the Zambia's SMEs in the manufacturing sector, the study found that firms with effective working capital management practices demonstrated better liquidity and creditworthiness. Banda and Moyo (2022) highlighted that the firms that employed strategies such as just-in-time inventory system and rigorous credit control measures, improved their cash flows and reduced financial risk.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research designs

The study employed a mixed-method design to examine the effectiveness of working capital management on the business performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the manufacturing industry of Kitwe District. Quantifiable statistics was collected through structured forms, while qualitative acumens gotten by semi-structured interviews with SMEs operational supervisor. This method improves the rationality and profundity of results by capturing arithmetical inclinations together with related practices (Afza and Nazir, 2017).

3.2 Target Population

The target population for this study was SMEs operating manufacturing sector in Kitwe District. This population were chosen to provide understanding of what on the effectiveness of working capital management on business liquidity and profitability.

3.4 Sampling Size Determination

The sample size of 200 respondents was used during data collection from the manufacturing SMEs in Kitwe District.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

The study utilized both primary and secondary data collection approaches. The data was collected through semi-structured questionnaire, interviews and focus group. While secondary data was sourced from financial reports, industry, journals and former researchers on WCM and SMEs performance in Zambia.

3.6 Data analysis

Quantitative data collected from the questionnaires was analyzed using the descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and frequency distribution was used to summarize WCM practices. Inferential statistics, specifically, correlation and regression analysis, was employed to establish the relationship between WCM efficiency and business performance.

3.7 Triangulation

Triangulation was employed to enhance the reliability and validity of the research. By using multiple data sources (quantitative and qualitative), the study ensured a comprehensive analysis of WCM practices.

4. Findings and Discussions

4.1 Background characteristics

4.1.1 Position of Respondent in the Company

Figure 1 shows that (68.0%) of the respondents work as financial managers and the remaining (32.00%) of the respondents work as accountants.

Figure 1: Position within the company

4.1.2 Years of Experience

Figure 2 shows that 8.00% of the respondents indicated that they have worked in their current position for a period of less than a year. 19.00% of the respondents have worked in their current position for a period between 4-6 years and 73.00% of the respondents have worked in their current position for a period of between 1-3 years.

Figure 2: Years worked in current position

4.1.3 Company Size

Figure 3 has revealed that 21.00% of the respondents in the study have 51-100 employees, 22.00% of the respondents in the study have less than 10 employees and the remaining respondents 10.5% of the respondents have 10-50 employees.

Figure 3: Company size

4.2 Effect Of Working Capital Management On Profitability Of SMEs In The Manufacturing Sector In Kitwe District.

4.2.1 Inferential statistics

The hypotheses statements for the variables in this portion of the chapter were examined with the application of chi-square analysis to test the hypotheses and determine whether or not there is a relationship between the two variables between the two variables. The chi-square test was used to examine whether or not the statements made in the study hypothesis were valid or not according to the results from the study. according to the rejection criteria, when the p-value is less than 0.05, it is regarded as a less than 0.05, which allows us to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, which is in accordance with the rejection criterion allowing us to reject H0 and accept the alternative hypothesis. As result of null hypothesis being rejected, it means that the variables are somehow related to one another (Prša, 2020).

Pearson correlation coefficient was in the study to determine whether or not there was a significant relationship between variables during this phase of investigation. Pearson correlation coefficient was also used to determine the magnitude of the relationship, which was discussed in the section of chapter.

Pearson's correlation coefficient was to determine the strength of the linear relationship between variables. A correlation with a value of 0 indicates that there is no relationship between the two independent and dependent variables being compared. Pearson's correlation coefficients ranging from 0.10 to 0.29 are considered weak, 0.30 to 0.49 are considered medium, and 0.50 to 1.0 are considered strong; correlation (Creswell, 2016).

4.2.2 Testing for Hypothesis 1

In section hypothesis 1 of this study gets tested with Chi-square analysis and Pearson's correlation. This hypothesis was formulated to analyse the effect of working capital management on profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H₁: Working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H₀: Working capital management has no significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

Table 1: Working capital management and the profitability of SMEs chi-square test

	Test Statistics	
	Working capital management	The profitability of SMEs
Chi-Square	229.150 ^a	332.700 ^b
Df	14	13
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.3.

b. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 14.3.

The Chi-square test of association between working capital management and the profitability of SMEs presented in the above table, recorded a significant (p) value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 at a 95% significance level, which indicates that working capital management and the profitability of SMEs share a significant relationship.

This means that null hypothesis of this research (H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.) is, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which stated that (H_1 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district). The rejection of the null hypothesis means that an increase of working capital management will lead to an increase in the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district. The results of the chi-square also indicate that working capital management is a predictor of the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district. The results from the chi-square has also established that Working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association

Table 2: Working capital management and the profitability of SMEs Pearson’s correlation

		Working capital management	The profitability of SMEs
Working capital management	Pearson Correlation	1	.795**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
The profitability of SMEs	Pearson Correlation	.795**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The Pearson’s correlation momentum test between working capital management and the profitability of SMEs has a correlation coefficient of 0.795** and the correlation is statistically significant since the Sig (2-tailed) has a probability (p) value which is less than 0.05. This result means that the relationship between working capital management and the profitability of SMEs is strong, because the value of the Pearson’s correlation coefficient is between 0.50 to 1.0.

This means that null hypothesis of the research (H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.) is, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which stated that (H_1 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district).

The rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that an increase of working capital management will lead to an increase in the profitability of SMEs. The results of the Pearson’s correlation also mean that working capital management is predictor of the profitability of SMEs. The results from the Pearson’s correlation have further established that working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

4.3 Effect Of Working Capital Management On The Liquidity Of SMEs In The Manufacturing Sector In Kitwe District.

4.3.1 Testing for Hypothesis 2

In section hypothesis 2 of this study gets tested with Chi-square analysis and Pearson’s correlation. This hypothesis was formulated to establish the effect of working capital management on liquidity of SMEs in manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H_2 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

Table 3: Working capital management and liquidity of SMEs chi-square test Test Statistics

	Working capital management	Liquidity of SMEs
Chi-Square	229.150 ^a	565.490 ^b
Df	14	10
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

- a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.3.
- b. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 18.2.

The Chi-square test of association between working capital management and liquidity of SMEs presented in the above table, recorded a significant (p) value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 at a 95% significance level, which indicates that Working capital management and liquidity of SMEs share a significant relationship. This means that null hypothesis of this research (**H₀**: Working capital management has no significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.) is, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which stated that (**H₂**: Working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district)

The rejection of the null hypothesis means that an increase of working capital management will lead to an increase in the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the chi-square also show that Working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

The results from the chi-square have established that working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

Table 4: Working capital management and liquidity of SMEs Pearson’s correlation test

correlations

		Liquidity of SMEs	Working capital management
Liquidity of SMEs	Pearson Correlation	1	.957**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Working capital management	Pearson Correlation	.957**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson’s correlation between working capital management and liquidity of SMEs has a correlation coefficient of 0.957** and the correlation is statistically significant since the Sig (2-tailed) has a p value less than 0.05. This result means that the relationship between working capital management and liquidity of SMEs is very strong, because the value of the Pearson’s correlation coefficient is between 0.50 to 1.0. This means that null hypothesis of this research (**H₀**: Working capital management has no significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.) is, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which stated that (**H₂**: Working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.).

The rejection of the null hypothesis means that an increase of working capital management will lead to an increase in the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the Pearson’s correlation also indicate that working capital management is a predictor of liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector.

The results from the Pearson’s correlation have revealed that working capital management has a significant effect on the liquidity of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

Table 5: Results of hypotheses

Hypotheses statements	Statistical test used	(P) values	Result
H ₁	Chi-square, and Pearson’s correlation.	P<0.05	Accepted
H ₂	Chi-square and Pearson’s correlation	P<0.05	Accepted

According to the findings shown in Table 4.3.5, all of the hypothesis’s statements of this study were supported and validated.

4.4. Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic data revealed that 68% of the respondents were financial managers while 32% were accountants, indicating that the study was primarily captured the perspective of individuals directly involved in financial decisions making. In terms of experience, 73% had served in their position for 1 – 3 years, 19% for 4 – 6 years, and 8% for the less than a year, reflecting a work force with a moderate experience. Regarding the firm size, 22% of the respondents were from a very small enterprises (less than 10 employees), 10.5% from the small firms (10 – 50 employees), 21% from medium-sized enterprises (51 – 100 employees), providing diverse insights across the business scales.

4.4.2 Working Capital Management and Profitability of SMEs

The first objective was to analyze the effect of WCM on Profitability. The findings from both the chi-square test and Pearson correlation to demonstrate a strong positive relationship between WCM and profitability, with the correlation efficiency of 0.795, which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (WCM-Report 2025).

This implies that SMEs that adopt effective working capital practices such as prudent cash management, efficient receivable collection, and optimal inventory levels are more likely to experience higher profitability. These results support earlier studies in different contexts. For instance, Padachi (2006) found that efficient management of working capital components, especially inventory and receivables, enhance profitability among SMEs. Reeman and Nasr (2007) observed that reducing the cash conversion cycle significantly improves firm profitability in Zambia's context, where SMEs operate with the limited access to the external financing, the ability to efficiently recycle cash tied up in working capital is even more critical (Prša, 2020).

This study findings confirms that in Kitwe's manufacturing sector benefit from sound WCM practices in the terms of increased returns. However, the results also echo caution from the literature that the relationship between WCM and profitability is not always linear. For example, Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano (2007) argue that excessive liquidity, while risk, may result in missed investment opportunities and thus, lower profitability. Conversely, insufficient liquidity can lead to stock-outs and miss sales opportunities. Therefore, profitability is maximized when the SMEs maintain an optimal balance, ensure neither excessive nor inadequate investment in working capital.

4.4.3 Working Capital Management and Liquidity of SMEs

The second objective examined the effect of WCM on liquidity. The findings revealed a very strong positive relationship, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.957 ($p < 0.05$). This finding demonstrates that actually SMEs in Kitwe that manage their working capital effectively are significantly more capable of maintaining sufficient liquidity to meet short-term obligations. However, the implication is that WCM usually directly influences the ability of SMEs to sustain every single day operations without encounter any financial distress.

These findings agreed with the existing literature which emphasized that liquidity management is a cornerstone of WCM (Deloof (2003). SMEs that efficiently manage receivables and payables cycles enhance their liquidity positions, reducing the likelihood of insolvency (Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano, 2007). Limited access to credit makes liquidity management through internal cash flows is important for SMEs sustainability. In Zambia's high-cost borrowing environment, efficiency WCM practices helps SMEs avoid reliance on expensive loans thereby improving liquidity.

The study further confirms that the theoretical perspective of how liquidity and profitability are interlinked. While liquidity ensures that firms meet their obligations, excessive emphasis on holding liquid assets can reduce profitability (Garcia-Teruel and Martinez-Solano, 2007). The SMEs that usually focuses to maintain optimal level of liquidity, while simultaneously investing in growth, were those that achieved the better financial outcomes.

In summary, effective WCM significantly influences profitability, liquidity, solvency and growth of the SME in the manufacturing sector of Kitwe District. WCM is found to be very vital determinant of business performance, particularly in resource constrained environments.

5. Conclusion, Recommendations and Summary

5.1 Conclusion

The findings demonstrated a consistent and significant relationship between WCM and the performance of SMEs in manufacturing sectors in Kitwe. WCM is not just an operational necessity but a strategic determinant of profitability and liquidity. With regards to profitability, firms that carefully balanced their receivables, payables and inventory cycles and reported higher levels of profit. The chi-square test revealed a statistically association, while Pearson correlation of 0.795 confirmed a strong positive relationship between WCM and profitability. On liquidity, SMEs with sounds WCM policies were better able to meet their short-term obligations. The regression results confirmed that liquidity was significantly influenced by how receivables and payables were managed.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings the following are the specific recommendations that have been proposed:

- i. SMEs should prioritize structured working capital policies that focus on optimizing cash conversion cycle. Managers should enforce strict receivables collection policies and avoid overextension of credit to customers
- ii. SMEs should improve their internal financial management systems, adopting computerized accounting systems to enhance monitoring of cash inflows and outflows.

iii. Policymakers should create an enabling environment that supports SMEs in their efforts to manage working capital effectively, improving access to affordable credit and encouraging digital financial solutions.

5.3 Summary

Working capital management has a significant effect on the profitability and liquidity of SMEs in Kitwe District. Efficient management of receivables, payables, and inventory cycles directly improves profitability. SMEs with sound WCM practices sustain short-term obligations without overreliance on costly borrowing.

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